

Bullacris unicolor Bladder grasshopper

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© V. Couldridge

Group: Insect

Size: 4 cm length

Distribution:

Bullacris unicolor occurs predominantly along the west coast of South Africa, in the Northern Cape and Western Cape, with isolated populations along the southern coast into the Eastern Cape.

Importance:

Bladder grasshoppers are unusual insects, largely endemic to Southern Africa and highly specialised for sound communication. Male *Bullacris unicolor* produce loud calls using an inflated abdomen that amplifies sound. Common in Namaqualand during spring, the species is known locally for its distinctive night-time “hekiejee” call.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 259 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.97 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 6.3 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.7% [Single: 93.2%, Duplicated: 4.5%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 19 687.55 kilobases

Contig number: 5192

Sample Contributor contact details:

Vanessa Couldridge

University of the Western Cape

vcouldridge@uwc.ac.za

DIPLOMICS
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

Date Published: 2026-06-09

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20608208>

